

HEMATOLOGICAL AND IMMUNOLOGICAL ASPECT THAT INFLUENCED BY DIETARY FENUGREEK OR/AND ALFA-ALFA IN THE BROILERS

Fatima Abbas Majeed¹, Ali Redha Abid², Ali j.AL-Nuaimi³

1,2,3 Department of Public Health\ College of Veterinary Medicine \ University of Kerbala
Email: Fatima@s.uokerbala.edu.iq¹ Aliredha.a@uokerbala.edu.iq², ali.j@uokerbala.edu.iq³

Abstract

This study, carried out to study the effect of dietary fenugreek, alfalfa and their mixture in broiler diet on some physiological traits and immunity of broilers. The experiment was conducted in special field during a period for 35 days. The study involved 120 one-day unsexed Ross 308 chicks, that were divided into four groups (30 birds/group) with three replicated (10 birds/replicate), the first group (control): chicks were fed on a basal diet without addition (G1), the second group fed on a basal diet with 2.5 gm fenugreek powder/Kg diet (G2), the third group fed on a basal diet with 2.5 gm alfalfa powder/Kg diet (G3), the fourth group was fed on a basal diet with 2.5 gm fenugreek and 2.5 gm alfalfa powder/Kg diet (G4). Blood samples were collected for biochemical parameters at 17th day and 35th day of age. The result revealed there were significant increase ($P \leq 0.05$) in total protein, globulin and albumin with a significant decrease ($p \leq 0.05$) in the cholesterol, triglycerides and low density lipoprotein (LDL) while the high density lipoprotein (HDL) recorded a significant increase ($p \leq 0.05$), also significant decreases of aspartate transaminase (AST) and alanine transaminase (ALT) that present in the addition groups as compared with the control, the anti-body titer against New castle disease and infection bursal disease showed a significant increase ($P \leq 0.05$) in addition group as compared with the control.

Key words: fenugreek, alfalfa, immunity, broiler.

Introduction: *Poultry industry is one of the most dynamic and growing divisions in the world, especially in growing countries (Alkhalaf et al., 2010). The global poultry sector is expected to grow continuously ever since the demand for meat is continuously increasing by the populations increase (Mottet and Tempio, 2017). 801*

Consumers' growing interest in bioactive components of natural origin has resulted as use of herbal plants, as beneficial ingredients in the industries of feed and food production (Sacchetti et al., 2005) 899

Fenugreek (Trigonella foenum graecum) is one of the herbs having multi-functional characteristics such as antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, hypoglycemic, hypolipidemic, hypocholesteremic, antipyretic, and antioxidative properties on animals, It contains several vital compounds, including flavonoids, alkaloids, saponins, vitamins, minerals, carbohydrates, and proteins (Srinivasan, 2006). (711) other roles of fenugreek including anti-atherosclerotic effect, and immunity stimulation have been confirmed (Zadehet et al., 2015). 757

Alfaalfa (*Medicago sativa* L.) is one of the cheapest sources of protein from the aspect of high yields and low production costs (Radović *et al* 2009). It is feedstuff with high fiber and with low metabolizable energy (Donalson *et al.*, 2005). It is a readily available, high protein, high fiber feedstuff with one of the slowest rates of passage through the avian system (Garcia *et al.*, 2000)(835). Due to the high content of saponins (2–3% of dry matter) alfalfa meal has hypocholesterolaemic, anticarcinogenic, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant activities (Englmaierova *et al.*, 2019) 801. Alfalfa is also a natural source of xanthophylls, which, when deposited in the skin and shanks give poultry carcasses a desirable yellow color (Dansky, 1971). 802

So the objectives of this study were to evaluate the effects of fenugreek, alfalfa and their mixture on blood parameters and immune response of broiler chickens.

Material and method This study was carried out in a private breeding hall, from 22 Jan. to 26 Feb. / 2022. A total of 120 day-old broiler chickens was taken and randomly allocated into 4 groups with 3 replicates per group (10 chicks per replicate). G1 was used as a control, while the chicks of G2 fed basal diet with 2.5 gm of dry fenugreek leaves /kg diet, G3 fed basal diet with 2.5 gm dry alfalfa leaves powder/kg diet, G4 fed basal diet with 2.5 gm/kg dry fenugreek leaves and 2.5 gm dry alfalfa /kg diet.

Standard broiler diets for starter (0-21 day) and finisher (21-35 day) showed in table (1). The broiler chicks were housed in a litter system and provided *ad libitum* feed and water throughout the trial period. The temperatures were 33°C, 30°C, 28°C, 24°C and 22°C during the 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th and 5th weeks of age respectively. The lighting regime was 23:1 light-dark cycle. Table (2) showed the vaccination program.

Blood was collected from each group via brachial vein at days 17 and 35 of age, serum were separated, labeled and stored at -20°C until analysis, antibody titers against Newcastle Disease Virus and Infectious Bursal Disease virus in serum samples were detected at 35 days of age by using Enzyme Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA technique) for different groups (Spalatin *et al.*, 1973).

Data obtained from the present study were analyzed as one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) using Complete Randomized Design (CRD) procedure to SPSS 22.0 software (Corp, 2011). Four treatment means were separated by using a Duncan's analysis in level (0.05).

Table (1). Ingredients and ofchemical analysisexperimental diets.

Ingredient % Starter (1-21 day))	Starter (1-21 day)	Finisher (22-35 day)
Corn	30	30
Soya bean meal(44% protein)%	28	20
Wheat%	27.5	35.5
Animal Protean (50%)	10	10
Oil%	3	3
Salt%	0.3	0.3
Limestone%	1	1.2
Total	100	10

Chemical Analysis*of basal diet

Gross energy k cal/kg	3078	3125.2
Crude protein %	22.74	20.16
Energy/protein ration	135.35	155.07
Calcium %	0.97	1.0
Available Phosphate %	0.41	0.48
Methionine + cystein %	0.83	0.75
Lysine%	1.02	0.95
Methionine %	0.78	0.51

Chemical analysis according to(NRC, 1994).

Table (2) program of vaccination

Age of chicks (days)	Disease	Type of vaccine	Origin	Rout of vaccination.
1 st	Newcastle + Avian influenza+ bronchitis+ Infectiousbursal disease	Killed vaccine +MA5 +trans immune	Holland	Spray + injection
10 th	Newcastle disease	Clone 30 strain	Holland	Via drinking water
20 th	Newcastle disease	Clone30 strain	Holland	spray

The results:- Table (3) cleared the effect of fenugreek, alfalfa and their mixture on total protein, Albumin and Globulin at 17th days of age, the results showed a significant increase($P \leq 0.05$) in

addition groups as compared with control, The same results were achieved at the 35th day of age in table (4), table (5) showed a significant decrease ($P \leq 0.05$) in the serum cholesterol, triglyceride and LDL concentration of the addition groups at 17th days of age as compared with the control, since G4 had a lowest value as compared to other groups and G3 lower than G2, while the control recorded higher value, HDL recorded a significant increase ($P \leq 0.05$) in addition groups, especially G2, as compared to control, also this results match with that at 35th day of age table (6),

Table (7) revealed a significant difference ($P \leq 0.05$) in AST and ALT in all groups, G2, G3 and G4 groups showed a significant decrease ($P \leq 0.05$) in AST and ALT as compared with the control group. Table finding also revealed that there were no significant differences between G2 and G3 groups, while there were a significant decrease ($P \leq 0.05$) in value of AST and ALT at G4 as compared with other experimental groups, It could be noted that there is a statistical similarity in the results of AST and ALT among the groups, the antibody titers against Newcastle disease and infectious bursal viruses at 35th of age after adding fenugreek, alfalfa and their mixture in the diet of broilers that cleared in table (8), in present study there is a significant increase of G2, G3 and G4 on antibody titer against ND and Gumboro if compared with control group

Table (3) Effect of fenugreek, alfalfa and their mixture on Protein profile of broilers at 17th days of age (Mean±SE):

Total protein, albumin and globulin (gm/L)				
Group Parameter	G1	G2	G3	G4
Total protein (gm/L)	1.80 ±0.05 C	2.56 ±0.07 a	2.24 ±0.05 b	2.33 ±0.06 a
Albumin (gm/L)	0.64 ±0.02 b	0.88 ±0.04 a	0.68 ±0.04 b	0.98 ±0.04 a
Globulin (gm/L)	1.12 ±0.04 C	1.68 ±0.06 ab	1.56 ±0.05 b	1.74 ±0.04 a

Different letters in the same row showed a significant difference at ($p < 0.05$), G1(Control): basal diet only, G2: 2.5 gm/kg diet Fenugreek, G3: 2.5 gm/kg diet alfalfa, G4: 2.5 gm/kg diet Fenugreek + 2.5 gm/kg diet alfalfa.

Table (4) Effect of fenugreek, alfalfa and their mixture on total Protein, albumin and globulin of broilers at 35th days of age (Mean±SE):

Total Protein ,albumin and globulin (gm/L)				
Group parameter	G1	G2	G3	G4
Total protein (gm/L)	1.94 ±0.05 C	2.68 ±0.04 b	2.92 ±0.05 a	2.74 ±0.02 b
Albumin (gm/L)	0.64 ±0.02 B	0.98 ±0.04 a	0.96 ±0.05 a	0.90 ±0.05 a
Globulin (gm/L)	1.30 ±0.04 D	1.70 ±0.03 c	1.96 ±0.02 a	1.84 ±0.02 b

Different letters in the same row showed a significant difference at ($p < 0.05$), G1(Control):basal diet only,G2: 2.5 gm/kg diet Fenugreek, G3:2.5 gm/kg diet alfalfa, G4: 2.5 gm/kg diet Fenugreek +2.5 gm/kg diet alfalfa .

Table (5):Effect of fenugreek, alfalfa and their mixture on lipid profile of broilers at 17th days (Mean±SE):

Lipid profile (mg/dl)				
Group parameter	G1	G2	G3	G4
Cholesterol (mg/dl)	175.60 ±0.75 A	137.00 ±1.18 b	122.6 ±1.25 c	116.80 ±1.62 d
Triglyceride (mg/dl)	75.00 ±1.00 A	56.40 ±0.51 b	47.60 ±1.50 c	36.90 ±3.28 d
HDL (mg/dl)	52.60 ±0.51 D	86.00 ±0.32 a	61.80 ±0.80 c	75.80 ± 0.80 b
LDL (mg/dl)	68.40 ±0.68 A	54.60 ±0.81 b	49.00 ±0.55 C	45.40 ±0.93 d

Different letters in the same row showed a significant difference at ($p \leq 0.05$), G1(Control):basal diet only,G2:2.5 gm/kg diet Fenugreek, G3:2.5 gm/kg diet alfalfa , G4: 2.5 gm/kg diet Fenugreek +2.5 gm/kg diet alfalfa .

Table (6)Effect of fenugreek, alfalfa and their mixture on lipid profile of broilers at 35th days (Mean±SE):

lipid profile (mg/dl)				
Group parameter	G1	G2	G3	G4
Cholesterol (mg/dl)	188.8 ±0.66 A	177.8 ±1.43 b	115.4 ±1.54 c	81.8 ±1.02 d
Triglyceride (mg/dl)	85.8 ±0.66 A	60.4 ±0.51 b	53.8 ±0.73 c	45.2 ±0.37 d
HDL (mg/dl)	51.2 ±1.16 C	66.2 ±0.66 a	58.0 ±0.95 b	65.6 ±1.03 a
LDL (mg/dl)	80.0 ±1.58 A	55.8 ±0.66 b	52.0 ±0.89 bc	50.0 ±1.67 c

Different letters in the same row showed a significant difference at ($p \leq 0.05$), G1(Control):basal diet only,G2:2.5gm/kg diet Fenugreek, G3:2.5 gm/kg diet alfalfa , G4:2.5gm/kg diet Fenugreek +2.5 gm/kg diet alfalfa .

Table(7) Effect of fenugreek and alfalfa and their mixture on liver function enzymes of broilersat 35th days(Mean±SE):

AST, ALT (U/100ml)				
Group parameter	G1	G2	G3	G4
AST (U/100ml)	655.2 ±2.06 a	537.8 ±4.16 b	526.0 ±6.3 b	423.2 ±4.39 c
ALT (U/100ml)	14.8 ±0.37 a	10.0 ±0.45 b	9.8 ±0.49 b	7.4 ±0.68 c

Different letters in the same row showed a significant difference at ($p < 0.05$), G1(Control):basal diet only,G2:2.5gm/kg diet Fenugreek ,G3:2.5 gm/kg diet alfalfa , G4:2.5gm/kg diet Fenugreek +2.5 gm/kg diet alfalfa .

Table (8) Effect of fenugreek, alfalfa and their mixture on humeral immunity of broilerchicks at 35th days of the study (Mean± SE).

ND,IBD antibody titers				
Group parameter	G1	G2	G3	G4

NDv Antibody titter	9000 ±35.64 D	9800 ±35.04 c	10100 ±14.62 b	10990 ±17.73 a
IBDv Antibody titter	6000 ±17.50 D	7502 ±17.94 c	7803 ±5.95 b	9004 ±34.76 a

Different letters in the same row showed a significant difference at ($p < 0.05$), G1(Control):basal diet only,G2:2.5gm/kg diet Fenugreek ,G3:2.5 gm/kg diet alfalfa , G4:2.5gm/kg diet Fenugreek +2.5 gm/kg diet alfalfa ,(ND)Newcastle disease ,(IBD) Gumboro.

DISCUSSION :

The results of the current study showed a significant increase in total protein, globulin and albumin in the addition group (G2,G3and G4) as compared with control, the increment in total serum proteins might be attributed mainly to that fenugreek can stimulate the thyroid gland directly of serum increased significantly and led to increase serum protein content(Azoua, 2001), these results agree with Hassan, (2000) who reported that the total protein and globulin of serum increased significantly by feeding broiler chicks on additive diets with fenugreek seeds.

An increased total protein content in the blood plasma of the alfalfa groups may be due to the positive effect of the xanthophyll protein content of the alfalfaon protein metabolism in the animal body(Grela *et al.*,2008) is as other authors suggest attribute to biologically active substances, such as saponins with their beneficial properties that promote effective utilization of dietary proteins(Ender *et al.*, 1996). this result agrees with Elkomy and Elghalid, (2014) who found that the plasma total protein and albumin were progressively increased in alfalfa groups as compared to the control.

Our study revealed a significant decreases ($P \leq 0.05$) in TC and triglyceride in G2, G3and G4 as compared with control. HDL values also increased significantly in addition groups as compared with control, particularly G2, while, LDL values presented adverse result to HDL in trial groups that were significantly decrease ($P \leq 0.05$) speciallyatthe G4 as compared with control,a reduction in the serum cholesterol level when dietary supplements of fenugreek broiler diets could be due to the presence of saponins and resins in fenugreek such as hemicelluloses, mucilage, tannin and pectin which inhibit bile acid, help lesser LDL-cholesterol and inhibit intestinal cholesterol absorption, thereby reducing blood cholesterol levels which might have reduced the bile acid and cholesterol absorption from the intestine(Petit *et al.*, 1995).

These results agree with Abed El Latif and Enas,(2021)who reported that feeding broiler chicks on a diet containing fenugreek lowered total plasma lipids and cholesterol levels. El-Hack *et al.*, (2015) explained that a decrease in chicken serum total cholesterol concentration and an increase

in high density lipoprotein cholesterol concentration due to fenugreek seed extract supplementation improvement in HDL led to reduce in LDL-cholesterol.

Our study showed that there were significantly decrease in the TC, TG and LDL in G3 and G4, which supplement with alfalfa as compared with the control, the best value recorded in G4 that received mixture of fenugreek and alfalfa, numerous researchers explain that high saponin levels (approximately 2–3%) were found in the groups additive with alfalfa which are known for the hypocholesterolemic (Francis *et al.*, 2002), saponins which are involved in the reduction of total cholesterol levels through the formation of insoluble complexes with cholesterol, which inhibits their absorption. Besides, they increase secretion of bile, gastric, and intestinal juices (Khaleel *et al.*, 2005).

These results consistent with Mansoub and Myandoab, (2012) who reported that serum total cholesterol and triglycerides levels were significantly reduced in group fed alfalfa compared to the control group, Guiwen *et al.*, (2021) reported that the TG was moderately lower in the Alfalfa supplementation groups at the level 50 gm /kg diet than in the control.

AST or ALT levels of blood are very important as they are indicators of liver status, current, present study indicated that there were a significant decrease ($P \leq 0.05$) in AST and ALT of G2, G3 and G4 groups as compared with the control, alkaloids, including trigonelline, carpine, and gentianine compounds are the most important alkaloids of fenugreek, it seems vitamins A and B1 component of fenugreek are effective in liver function and might decrease ALT and AST enzyme levels (Moradi *et al.*, 2013).

Consistent with the results of Jafar *et al.*, (2021) who indicated all groups that fed on fenugreek showed a significant improved hepatic function with significantly decreased in the AST and ALT level, which explained that, liver and its normal functioning is very vital in broilers where Saponin, vit. A, B1, C, nicotinic acid, and alkaloids are active ingredient which can act as immunomodulators and liver tonic components. Guiwen *et al.*, (2021) showed that alfalfa supplementation groups at the ratio 25 gm/kg was significantly lower the level of AST than that in the other groups.

Antibody titer against NDV and IBDV at 35 day of broilers age indicated that the G2, G3 and G4, which supplemented with 2.5 gm fenugreek, 2.5 alfalfa and combination of these two herbs respectively, revealed achieved higher and best titer against two studied diseases, because it have higher antibody titer, but the control recoded lowest titer against these viruses, the cause of these increases might be immunomodulating ability of these herbs to improve immunity by active components such as flavonoids, steroid saponin, or by raising the weight of lymphatic tissue (Abid *et al.*, 2011) these results approve with Bin-Hafeez *et al.*, (2003) who recorded that the fenugreek increase the immunity of broiler at 24 and 34 day, thus These herbs increase the cellularity of the thymus gland as well as the bone marrow, they also noticed increasing the action of macrophage

and humeral response by plaque forming cell assay , as just as Abed and Fateh, (2014) showed that adding of 1% fenugreek in the broiler chicken diet recorded a high antibody titer against ND_v and IBD_v .

In current study saponins and flavonoids have the function of immune improvement, which has been found in alfalfa polysaccharides (Jiang and Yu, 2005). Polysavone, a compound containing the three active ingredients., exhibited obvious activity in improving immunity, may be as a result of synergism among its active ingredients or the simple combination of the functions of each component.

Another explanation might be that the plant with feed additive properties can decrease the pathogenic microorganisms, motivating the immune system, and then strengthen the immune system of broilers. Newly it was resumed that, the supplementation with alfalfa 4%, 6%, and 7.3% in the diet of broiler chickens revealed increasing the proliferation of useful bacteria, thus immune strengthening against pathogenic bacteria (Gulizia and Downs, 2020; Pliego *et al.*, 2020).899

Conclusion In the present study some of beneficial acts toward using fenugreek and alfalfa on biochemical and some immune parameters on broiler chicks were demonstrated. We may conclude it will be possible that the fenugreek and alfalfa concentration at 2.5 gm/kg diet had a good immunomodulatory ,liver tonic effect,improve total protein and it also could reduce the risk of hyperlipidemia.

References

- ❖ Abed A .R. and. Fateh .O .K 2014. Efect of mint and fenugreek and mixture on production and immunity of brioler .Veterinary Medicine College- Kerbala University . Journal of Kerbala University , Vol. 12 No.2 Scientific.
- ❖ Abed El Latif M. A. and Enas M.A.Toson,(2021) Effect of using Fenugreek seeds powder as feed additive in broiler chicks diet on growth performance and some metabolic responses, Egyptian Poultry Science Journal, Vol. (41) (I):P (31-43).
- ❖ Abid,A.A.;wahab,H.M.and Israa.N.A.(2011).Effect of fenugreek and rosemary on some blood parameters,bacterial counts and immunity after ND vaccination of broilers .Scientific Conference of Veterinary Medicine .University of Kufa.28-29.
- ❖ Alkhalf, A., Alhaj, M. and Al-homidan, I. (2010) Influence of probiotic supplementation on blood parameters and growth performance in broiler chickens. Saudi J Biol Sci 17, 219–225.
- ❖ Azoua, H.M.(2001). Effect of hot pepper and fenugreek seeds supplementation on broiler diets. Ph.D. Thesis, Egypt. pp: 181.
- ❖ Bin-Hafeez, B., Haque, R., Parvez, S., Pandey, S., Sayeed, I. and Raisuddin, S. 2003. Immunomodulatory effects of fenugreek (*Trigonella foenum graecum*) extract on mice. International Immunopharmacology, 3: 257-265.
- ❖ Corp, I. (2011). IBM SPSS statistics for windows, version 22.0. IBM Corp Armonk, NY.

- ❖ Dansky, L. M. 1971. A role for alfalfa in high efficiency broiler rations. *Poult. Sci.* 50:1569–1574.
- ❖ Donalson, L. M., Kim, W. K., Woodward, C. L., Herrera, P. Kubena, L. F., Nisbet, D. J., Ricke, S. C. 2005. Utilizing Different Ratios of Alfalfa and Layer Ration for Molt Induction and Performance in Commercial Laying Hens. *Poultry Science*, vol. 84, no. 3, p. 362-369.
- ❖ El-Hack MEA , Alagawany(M. 2015).Performance, egg quality, blood profile, immune function, and antioxidant enzyme activities in laying hens fed diets with thyme powder. *J Anim Feed Sci*;24(2):127-133.
- ❖ Elkomy A. E. and Elghalid, O. A. 2014. Physiological Performance of Broiler Chicks Fed on *Medicago sativa* Seeds as Natural Source of Isoflavones. *Asian J. Poult. Sci.*, 8: 97- 105.
- ❖ Ender K., Kuhn G., Nurnberg K., and Jacques K.A. (1996). Effect of *Yucca schidigera* extract on performance, carcass evaluation and skatole content of fattening boars. *J. Anim. Sci*, 74, (Suppl. 1): 47.
- ❖ Englmaierova, M., Skřivan, M., & Vit, T. (2019). Alfalfa meal as a source of carotenoids in combination with ascorbic acid in the diet of laying hens. *Czech Journal of Animal Science*, 64(1), 17-25
- ❖ Francis GZ, Kerem H, Makkar P, Becker K. 2002. The biological action of saponins in animal systems: a review. *Br J Nutr.* 88:587–605.
- ❖ Garcia, J., Caraban˜o, R., Pere´z-Alba, L., de Blas, J. C. 2000. Effect of fiber source on cecal fermentation and nitrogen recycled through cecotrophy in rabbits. *Journal of Animal Science*, vol. 78, p. 638-646
- ❖ Grela E.R., Semeniuk W and Florek M. 2008. Effects of proteinxanthophylls (PX) concentrate of alfalfa additive to crude protein-reduced diets on nitrogen excretion, growth performance and meat quality of pigs. *J Central Eur Agric*, 9, 669–676
- ❖ Guiwen He, Li Zhao, Md Safiqur Rahaman Shishir, Yajin Yang, Qingqing Li, Long Cheng and Aiwei Guo (2021) .Influence of alfalfa meal, as a source of dietary fibre, on growth performance, development, pH of gastrointestinal tract, blood biochemical profile, and meat quality of broilers, *Journal of Applied Animal Research*, 49:1, 431-439.
- ❖ Hassan, M.S.H. (2000): Physiological studies on egg cholesterol and immunity in layers. Ph.D. thesis, Animal production Dept., Faculty of Agriculture, Cairo University.
- ❖ Jafar T. , Seyedhesamodin E.* , Saiedeh N. , Ali M. and Mahmood Ahmadih.2021. Effect of *Trigonella foenum-graecum* L. on Immune Function and Liver Activity of Ross 308 Broiler Chickens. *Journal of Medicinal Plants and By-products* (2022) Special Issue: 59-65.
- ❖ Khaleel, A.E., GAD, M.Z., EL-Maraghy, S.A., Hifnawy, M.S., Abdel-Sattar, E.(2005). Study of hypocholesterolemic and antiatherosclerotic properties of *Medicago sativa* cultivated in Egypt. *J. Food and Drug Anal.* 13, 212-218.
- ❖ Mansoub, N. H. and Myandoab, M. P. 2012. Effect of dietary inclusion of alfalfa (*Medicago sativa*) and black cumin (*Nigella sativa*) on performance and some blood metabolites of Japanese quail. *Res. Opin. Anim. Vet. Sci.*, 2(1), 7-9.

- ❖ Morad, i N., Didarshetaban, MB., Reza, H., Pour, S.(2013). Fenugreek (*Trigonella foenum-graecum* L.) As a Valuable Medicinal Plant. *Int J Adv Biol Biomed Res.*;1:922 -31.
- ❖ Mottet, A., & Tempio, G. (2017). Global poultry production: current state and future outlook and challenges. *World's Poultry Science Journal*, 73(2), 245-256.
- ❖ NRC.(1994): National Research Council. Nutrient requirements of poultry. 9th rev. ed. National Academy Press, Washington, USA.
- ❖ Petit, P., Y. Sauvair and D. Hillaire, 1995. Steroid saponins from Fenugreek seeds: Extraction, purification and pharmacological investigation on feeding behavior and plasma cholesterol. *Steroids*, 60: 674-680.
- ❖ Radović, J., Sokolović, D., Marković, J., Radovica, J., Sokolović, D., Marković, J.2009. Alfalfa – most important perennial forage legume in animal husbandry. *Biotechnology in Animal Husbandry*, Belgrade-Zemun: Institute for Animal Husbandry, vol. 25, no. 5-6, p. 465-475.
- ❖ Sacchetti, G. et al. (2005). Comparative evaluation of 11 essential oils of different origin as functional antioxidants, antiradical, and antimicrobials in foods. *Food Chemistry*, 91(4), 621-632.
- ❖ Spalatin, J.; Hanson, R. P. and Joes, T. D. (1973). Edema of the eyelid and face of chickens exposed to viscerotropic type of Newcastle virus. *Avian diseases*. 17: 623-628.
- ❖ Srinivasan, K. (2006). Fenugreek (*Trigonella foenum-graecum*): A review of health beneficial physiological effects. *Food-Reviews-International*, 22, 203–224.
- ❖ Zadeh JB, kor NM, Olfati A. (2015)The Effects of Different Levels Aqueous Extract of Fenugreek (*Trigonella foenum-graecum* L.) on Performance and Immune Response of Laying Hens. *J Essent Oil -Bearing Plants.*;18:1476 -81.